

20th ISCB **STUDENT COUNCIL** SYMPOSIUM

Montreal, Canada
12th July 2024

PROGRAM BOOKLET

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Welcome to SCS2024

Dear Participants,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 20th ISCB Student Council Symposium (SCS2024)!

This year marks a special milestone as we celebrate two decades of bringing together passionate students and early-career researchers in Computational Biology and Bioinformatics. SCS2024 has been a dynamic and exciting event, where knowledge, collaboration, and innovation have taken the center stage.

With a hybrid format designed to be inclusive and accessible, we were thrilled to present a variety of sessions, including inspiring keynote speeches, thought-provoking discussions, oral and flash talks, and interactive poster presentations. These sessions were tailored to foster engagement, spark new ideas, and create opportunities for meaningful collaboration across disciplines and borders.

Beyond the sessions, we have crafted unique opportunities for networking, helping you forge connections that extend well beyond the symposium. Whether you are joining us in person or virtually, you have the chance to interact with fellow researchers, mentors, and experts, creating bonds that will shape the future of the field.

A heartfelt thank you goes out to our participants, sponsors, volunteers, and the ISCB for their unwavering support in making this event possible. Your contributions are what make SCS a vibrant and thriving community!

As we embark on this collective journey, let us embrace the values of curiosity, innovation, and collaborative growth. The future of Computational Biology is ours to shape—together.

Welcome to SCS2024! We look forward to engaging with you and trust that this symposium will inspire, challenge, and empower you in your professional and academic pursuits.

Ana Isabel Castillo Orozco & Miguel Fernández Martín

Chairs, Organizing Committee
ISCB Student Council Symposium 2024

Organizing team

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This booklet was designed and edited by Miriam Poley Gil, Iria Pose Lagoa and Sebastián Urquiza Zurich on behalf of #SCS2024. It was supervised by Miguel Fernández Martín.

This booklet was inspired by the program booklet of #SCS2023 (<https://zenodo.org/records/8173977>), which was inspired by the program booklet of #ASCS2022 (<https://zenodo.org/record/7934696>) as a template.

Disclaimer

The ISCB Student Council has made all efforts to provide accurate information but does not guarantee the correctness of any information provided in this booklet. The ISCB Student Council is a committee of the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB), which is incorporated as a 501(c)(3) non-profit corporation in the United States.

Supported by

The International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB) is a recognized 501(c)(3) organization based in the United States. As a global society, ISCB is dedicated to advocating for and advancing scholarship, research, training, outreach, and inclusive community building in computational biology and related professions.

Membership in ISCB reflects a commitment to the growth and advancement of computational biology. As an international non-profit organization, ISCB brings together members from the global bioinformatics and computational biology communities. The society serves its members worldwide by organizing high-quality conferences, publishing research, and sharing reports on methodologies and tools. It also disseminates key information about bioinformatics resources and industry developments while actively supporting training, education, career development, and networking opportunities. ISCB advocates for policies and resources that advance scientific progress and benefit society as a whole.

The ISCB Student Council is the student-led organization of the International Society for Computational Biology. Its mission is to foster the development of the next generation of computational biologists. This is achieved through scientific events, networking opportunities, soft skills training, educational resources, and career guidance, while also working to influence policy processes that impact science and education.

New England Biolabs (NEB) is a leader in the discovery and production of enzymes for molecular biology applications. The company is committed to advancing science and environmental stewardship. NEB fosters the development of future scientists by providing high-quality reagents, technical support, educational resources, and career guidance. The company also emphasizes personal and professional growth through creativity, teamwork, respect, and responsibility, while maintaining a casual campus-like working environment. NEB's unique corporate philosophy encourages dialogue and innovation, aiming to influence policies that impact science and education.

Acknowledgements

The success of the Student Council Symposium 2024 (#SCS2024) is attributed to the dedication of numerous individuals. We extend our gratitude to everyone involved in organizing this event throughout the year, whether their contributions were brief tasks or months of committed effort. Some efforts deserve special recognition:

Without the logistical support and invaluable advice of ISCB Chief Executive Officer Diane Kovats and Lead Technologist Seth Munholland, #SCS2024 would not have been possible. We sincerely appreciate their continued support.

Special thanks to the ISMB/ECCB 2024 organizing committee.

We also thank the ISCB-SC Executive Team for their guidance and timely advice.

#SCS2024 would like to thank our:

- **Keynote speakers:** Dana Pe'er PhD, Manuel Corpas PhD and Martin Steinegger PhD.
- **Round table discussion panelists:** Nils Gehlenborg PhD, Dan de Blasio PhD and Camila Castillo PhD.
- Reviewers for volunteering their time to contribute to this symposium's success and promote the next generation of bioinformaticians and computational biologists.
- All the authors who shared their valuable work with the scientific community through SCS2024.

Furthermore, we would like to thank everyone on the organizing and steering committee for their time and effort in realizing this event.

Bios

Keynote speakers

20th edition
**Student
Council
Symposium**
Montreal - July 2024 - Hybrid

keynote speakers

Manuel Corpas

is
SCS Founder,
Lecturer of Genomics,
Chief Scientist and Founder of
Cambridge Precision Medicine
at
University of Westminster,
University of Cambridge (UK)

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SCS Founder, Chief Scientific Director of Cambridge Precision Medicine, Lecturer at the Institute of Continuing Education and Scientific Programmer at the European Bioinformatics Institute

Dr. Manuel Corpas has a prolific career, authoring over 50 peer-reviewed scientific publications and authored a book titled 'Perfect DNA', delving into the broader implications surrounding genetic sequencing. He actively contributes to the scientific community, serving as a member of the scientific committee for the Personal Genomes Conference at the Wellcome Genome Campus, and as the scientific coordinator for the World Longevity Forum in Valencia. Manuel's expertise in genomics dates back to the early stages of his career, where he was among the pioneers in sequencing his own genome among others, which he documented as Corpasome. At the Sanger Institute, he developed innovative methodologies for the integration, visualization, and analysis of genomic data.

20th edition
**Student
Council
Symposium**
Montreal - July 2024 - Hybrid

keynote speakers

Dana Pe'er

is
Chair and Professor in
Computational and Systems
Biology Program
at
Sloan-Kettering Institute,
New York (USA)

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Chair and Professor in Computational and Systems Biology Program

Prof. Dana Pe'er is known for her innovative work in systems biology, particularly in the areas of cancer research and single-cell genomics. She has been a pioneer in the development of computational methods for analyzing single-cell RNA sequencing data that helped to identify novel cell types. She has applied systems biology approaches to unravel the complexity of cancer genomics and tumor microenvironments, integrating large-scale genomic, transcriptomic, and proteomic data to construct comprehensive models of cellular processes. Pe'er applies these methods to model biological questions around cellular plasticity and single-cell phenotypic variation in cancer, developmental biology, and immunology, including tumor microenvironments, metastasis and responses to treatments such as immunotherapy.

20th edition
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Symposium**
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keynote speakers

Martin Steinegger

is
Assistant Professor of
Bioinformatics
at
Seoul National University
(Korea)

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Associate Professor in Biological Sciences, Seoul National University

Prof. Martin Steinegger studied bioinformatics and computer science, primarily focused on the development of methods for predicting protein mutation effects. During his Ph.D. worked on computational methods to assemble, cluster and annotate metagenomic data. Later, he developed methods for the identification of pathogenic agents in infectious diseases, the detection of assembly contamination in public datasets and the annotation of missing exons in the human proteome. Currently, his work focuses on big data and machine learning to develop methods to analyze genomic and proteomic data. He also applied these techniques to other complex problems like assembling and annotating metagenomic sequencing data, detecting or removing incorrectly labeled genomic sequences as an expert on large scale sequence data analysis and method development.

Round table panelists

ROUND TABLE SPEAKER

Dan DeBlasio

"My research interests are broadly in algorithm design and analysis, and I take inspiration from biological problems."

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Assistant Professor of Computer Science, University of Texas at El Paso, USA

Prof. DeBlasio's research interests are broadly in applied machine learning as well as algorithm design and analysis, and he takes inspiration from biological problems but also from outside computational biology, most recently in identifying unresolved space objects using hyper- and multispectral telescope imaging. He was a member of the ISCB Student Council, serving many leadership roles, until 2019 and has been a member of ISCB for more than 10 years. He also participated in the round table of #SCS2023.

ROUND TABLE SPEAKER

Camilla-Castillo Vilchuaman

"My research interests span between microbial ecology, microbial evolution, microbial genomics and bioinformatics."

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President and founder of RSG-Peru

Dr. Camila Castillo's research interests are focusing on microbe ecology, as well as applied bioinformatics in these fields. Instructor in courses related to bioinformatics, basic programming, and microbiology. Her background is in biology and is also really passionate about science communication, writing and teaching (workshops) all around Latin America.

ROUND TABLE SPEAKER

Nils Gehlenborg

"The goal of my research is to improve human health by developing computational techniques and interfaces that enable scientists and clinicians to efficiently interact with biomedical data."

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Associate Professor of Biomedical and Informatics and Director of the Master of Biomedical Informatics program at Harvard Medical School

Prof. Nils Gehlenborg's research interests focus on data visualization and making it interpretable. His research group built a lot of software methods to aid people better interpret data (applications in clinical medicine). He got involved in the SC around 2005 because it was brand new and got curious about this new event. He participated in the organising of the first events and also served as chair of the Student Council for a year, before being elected for the Board of Directors as the Student Council Representative at the ISCB level.

Program

The program structure and highlights of SCS2024 are summarised below, details also available at <https://www.iscb.org/scs2024/scientific-programme>.

Time	Activity	Detail	Key Participants
09:00 - 09:15	Introduction and Welcome words	Participant check-in or arriving	SCS2024 Chairs: Ana Castillo Miguel Fernández
09:15 - 10:00	Keynote Speaker 1	Title: "Towards plasticity in the tissue context: Characterizing niches"	Dana Pe'er, PhD
10:00 - 11:05	Session 1: Molecular Biology and Omics	Oral Talks: three talks Flash Talks: four presentations	Presenters: Sofía Rodriguez Wisdom A. Akuruguru Ornit Nahman Juan Picon Cossio Samuel Davis Matthew T. Unger Jianlin Li
11:05 - 11:25	Coffee Break	Networking and refreshments	All participants
11:25 - 12:15	Session 2: Deep Learning	Oral Talks: three talks Flash Talks: one presentation	Presenters: Iria Pose Manoj M. Wagle Miriam Poley-Gil
12:15 - 13:00	Keynote Speaker 2	Title: "A Scientific Career Shaped by the Student Council"	Manuel Corpas, PhD
13:00 - 14:40	Lunch, Poster Session and Networking	Informal conversations and poster presentations with all participants	All participants
14:40 - 15:05	Session 3: Toolkits Development	Oral Talks: one talk Flash Talks: two presentations	Presenters: James W. Li Adeline McKie
15:05 - 15:15	Session 4: Education in Bioinformatics	Flash Talks: two presentations	Presenters: Sara Fumagalli Nilson Da Rocha
15:15 - 16:15	Round Table Discussion	Topic: "The Impact of Student Council in Your Personal and Scientific Trajectory"	Panelists: Nils Gehlenborg, PhD Dan Deblasio, PhD Camila Castrillo Vicahuaman, PhD

16:15 - 17:30	Keynote Speaker 3	Title: "Metagenomic sequence analysis: from protein sequences to structures"	Martin Steinegger, PhD
17:30 - 17:35	Introducing ISCB Student Council Activities	Overview of initiatives and opportunities	Presenter: Ana Castillo
17:35 - 17:55	Closing Remarks	Reflections on the day and acknowledgments	SCS2024 Chairs: Ana Castillo Miguel Fernández
17:55 - 18:00	Group Photo	All attendees and participants gather for a group picture	All participants

Round table (extended version)

The main questions asked of the roundtable panelists, by the committee or by the audience, are set out below summarizing the answers in 3 take-home messages.

1. How did you manage to deal with participation in the Student Council, as well as the other responsibilities of a young researcher (courses, workshops, ...).

Motivation and Passion: Dan found his involvement in the Student Council motivating, viewing it as a hobby rather than a burden, which made it easier to manage alongside his PhD.

Multitasking and Learning: Camila thrived on multitasking, balancing her role in leading the bioinformatics community in Peru with other side projects, and viewed her involvement as a valuable learning experience that improved her organizational skills over time.

Early Involvement and Commitment: Nils joined the Student Council before his PhD, and by the time he began his studies, his deep involvement made it feel like a natural extension of his routine. His drive to make the first symposium successful stemmed from a desire to prove students could effectively run such an event.

2. What are the specific skills that you only gain thanks to the Student Council and are unattainable from academia?

Motivation and Leadership Skills: Nils emphasized the importance of engaging in community efforts, highlighting how it helps understand what motivates people and provides valuable organizational skills applicable throughout one's career.

Adaptability and Inclusivity: Camila gained a mindset that values diverse perspectives, learning the importance of adapting to different cultural practices when organizing international events and accepting viewpoints beyond her own.

Salesmanship and Event Logistics: Dan highlighted the significance of salesmanship, particularly in promoting research, securing sponsorships, and selling events. He views these skills as essential practice for handling the logistics of large-scale events in any organizational context.

3. How much information should we share with our PIs/superiors about volunteer work?

Passion and Impact: Camila emphasized that her motivation for volunteering came from a desire to pursue diverse experiences, advising others to ensure their volunteer work is impactful and personally enriching.

Balancing Priorities: Dan encouraged students to engage in multiple activities as long as they maintain clear priorities, stressing the importance of balancing academic commitments while being transparent about one's involvement.

Positive Framing and Autonomy: Nils reinforced the idea that volunteer work should be framed as something that enhances your work, not detracts from it, and reminded others that their PI does not "own" their time, advocating for independence in managing such commitments.

4. Question for Camila. How do you take advantage of these skills working in Latin America, considering it is not as well-equipped for these kinds of events/organisations as other parts of the world?

Regional Focus and Networking: She highlights how research in Latin America often remains within the region due to language and socio-economic factors, but the key value lies in the connections formed within Latin America itself.

Student Council's Role: The Student Council provided her with a platform to build a network of Latin American researchers, facilitating the creation of a collaborative community.

Growth of the Community: She observes that this Latin American research community is now well-established and continues to expand.

5. Question to Dan and Nils. Given your seniority, what role do you think the Student Council leadership will play in the training of future scientists in the field of bioinformatics and computational biology?

Skill Development and Career Advancement: Nils emphasizes that the Student Council (SC) plays a crucial role in transmitting skills vital for academic careers, helping researchers gain leadership and organizational knowledge earlier. He believes that involvement in SC and RSGs can significantly impact the advancement of research and create professional opportunities.

Global Networking and Future of Science: Dan highlights the value of virtual connections, noting that the SC now enables junior researchers to network globally, which he sees as essential for the future of science.

Early Connections Matter: Nils further stresses the importance of making connections early in one's career, as these relationships are more impactful than those made later, once an individual is already established as a principal investigator (PI).

6. **Question from the audience: Can you share experiences in getting people involved in the SC? Also, what do you think would be the best(workable) strategy to establish new RSGs in regions that do not already exist (Africa)? Also, can you assure that next year (2025) some of your students will take part in the SC?**

Local Representation and Regional Needs: Camila emphasizes the importance of ensuring representation from all regions, not just major cities. She highlights the value of creating local nodes within the RSG Peru, as each region has unique interests that should be addressed in the broader bioinformatics community.

Commitment and Retention Challenges: Dan discusses the challenge of retaining participants and getting people to commit to the Student Council. He recalls efforts to establish RSGs in Africa, noting that success depended on passionate leadership, which can fade over time, leading to inactivity. He suggests replicating the European model to maintain a sustainable and active network.

Critical Mass and Resource Allocation: Nils suggests that a key issue may be the lack of a critical mass of interested individuals, which makes it difficult to sustain RSGs. He believes that increasing interest and participation in the SC can help alleviate the burden on a small group of people, making it easier to establish new RSGs, with support from ISCB resources.

7. **Question from the audience: As a graduate student, I have a long way to go in terms of career growth. I do realise the gap in my skills and I am working on closing it, but I would love to get some advice. Also, how can I be part of the SC and use it to my benefit?**

Overcoming Impostor Syndrome and Embracing Opportunities: Dan acknowledges the presence of impostor syndrome but emphasizes that the Student Council always offers opportunities for individuals to engage in tasks aligned with their interests, such as design and outreach.

Continuous Learning and Taking Action: Camila highlights that there will always be gaps in knowledge, but the key is to take action and learn as you go. She advises not to wait until you feel fully ready, but to dive in and grow through experience.

Comfort in Discomfort: Nils advises learning to be comfortable with discomfort, recognizing that growth often comes from stepping outside your comfort zone.

Awards and Recognition

The SCS2024 celebrated exceptional contributions from early-career researchers by recognizing outstanding poster and oral presentations. To ensure fairness and rigor, the evaluation process was conducted by a popular vote of all event participants.

Poster Presentation Awards

In the poster category, Sofia Rodriguez received the first-place award for her work on "Deep Analysis of Regulatory Networks Based on Single Cell Transcriptomics Reveals a System of Master Regulators for Rett Syndrome." Rodriguez's research shed light on the intricate regulatory mechanisms underlying Rett syndrome, providing crucial insights for therapeutic strategies. The second-place award went to Miriam Poley-Gil for her poster "Exploring the Biophysical Boundaries of Protein Families with Deep Learning Methods", which showcased innovative applications of deep learning to understand protein structure and function. Adeline McKie secured third place with her work on "Development and Application of the MultiSEp R Package to Identify Multiple Myeloma Achilles' Heels for Drug Discovery", combining computational and experimental techniques to pave the way for novel therapeutic targets in multiple myeloma.

Oral Presentation Awards

In the oral presentation category, Ornit Nahman earned the first-place award for her presentation "Cell Specific Priors Rescue Differential Gene Expression in Spatial Spot-Based Technologies", which introduced a groundbreaking framework for improving gene expression analyses in spatial transcriptomics. James W. Li was awarded with the second place for his talk entitled "FinaleToolkit: Accelerating Cell-Free DNA Fragmentation Analysis with a High-Speed Computational Toolkit" highlighting the development of a computational resource for advancing cell-free DNA research. Finally, Iria Pose-Lago achieved third place with her presentation "Unraveling Patient Heterogeneity Through Explainable AI and Network-Based Strategies", which employed advanced AI techniques coupled with network analysis to explore variability among patient populations.

These awards reflect the SCS's commitment to fostering scientific excellence and recognizing the next generation of researchers who push the boundaries of knowledge in computational biology.

Accepted abstracts

Long Talks (20 Minutes Slot)

TITLE: A - Z

1. Cell specific priors rescue differential gene expression in spatial spot-based technologies

Authors: Ornit Nahman, Tim J. Cooper and Shai S. Shen-Orr

Keywords: Spatial transcriptomics, Differentially expressed genes, Genes specificity, Deconvolution

Spatial transcriptomics (ST), a breakthrough technology, captures the complex structure and state of tissues. Several ST technologies now exist, most prominently spot-based platforms such as Visium. Despite ST's widespread usage and distinct data characteristics, the vast majority of studies continue to analyze ST data using algorithms built for older technologies, such as single cell (SC) and bulk RNA-seq. This is particularly the case when identifying differentially expressed genes (DEGs), however, it remains unclear if the approaches used are still valid for ST data. Here, we sought to characterize the performance of these methods by constructing an in-silico simulator of ST data with a controllable and known DEG ground truth. Surprisingly, our findings reveal little variation in the performance of classic DEG algorithms - all of which fail to accurately recapture known DEGs to significant levels. Importantly, we further demonstrate that cellular heterogeneity within spots is a primary cause of this poor performance and propose a simple gene-selection scheme, based on prior knowledge of cell-type specificity, to overcome this. Importantly, our approach outperforms existing data-driven methods and enhances DEG recovery and trustworthiness in ST data. Overall, our work details a conceptual framework that can be used upstream of any DEG algorithm to improve the accuracy of the results and of any subsequent downstream analysis.

2. Deep analysis of regulatory networks based on single cell transcriptomics reveals a system of master regulators for Rett syndrome

Authors: Sofia Rodriguez, Camilo Villaman, Mauricio Saez and Alberto J. Martin

Key words: Computational Modeling, Gene Regulatory Networks, Single-cell transcriptomics, Single-cell Trajectory analysis, Boolean Networks, Rett Syndrome

Rett syndrome is a mono-chromosomal disorder with a prevalence much higher in women (95% of all cases). This disease is characterized by difficulties to study its phenotype caused by an intrinsic heterogeneity of the brain tissues affected due to the stochastic silencing of the X chromosome. In addition, we are yet largely unaware of the cellular-autonomous and non-cellular autonomous alterations that occur in neuronal

populations because of this pathology. To try to overcome these issues, we performed a gene regulatory analysis, from human organoid single cell transcriptomic data. We first performed a trajectory analysis to understand the data characteristics, followed by generation of pseudo-time-based gene regulatory networks to assess non-cellular autonomous processes. These approaches made it possible to show differences in the distribution of cells and their developmental differences. From the regulatory networks, it was possible to identify the absence of a regulatory mechanism associated with non-coding transcription factors not previously described for Dopaminergic neurons. These results served to postulate the existence of systemic master regulators, which we further evaluated with dynamic Boolean models per cell type.

3. Exploring the biophysical boundaries of protein families with deep learning methods

Authors: Miriam Poley-Gil, Maria I. Freiberger, Alin Banka, Michael Heinzinger, Noelia Ferruz, Alfonso Valencia and R. Gonzalo Parra

Key words: Protein Design, Reverse Folding, Protein Frustration, Biophysical Characterisation

Recently, Deep Learning models have revolutionised the Molecular Biology field allowing us to explore the intricate interplay between protein sequence, structure and function faster. To understand what they are capturing and generating we have combined state-of-the-art protein models for inverse folding (such as ProstT5 and ProteinMPNN) and for sequence generation (such as ProtGPT2 and ZymCTRL) with biophysical analyses. We have studied conservation patterns of local energetic frustration in artificial datasets to shed light on the evolutionary processes leading to the diversification of some protein families, under the assumption that proteins are optimised for folding and stability, but also evolutionarily selected to function. We have developed a tool called FrustraEvo that measures such conservation within and between protein families (available in full on the server <https://frustraevo.qb.fcen.uba.ar/>). We found that most of the highly frustrated native residues are related to functional aspects. These functional residues are mostly recovered by sequence generation models, suggesting that there are alternative ways to design proteins instead of the way explored by evolution. In the case of catalytic sites, they are also recovered by inverse folding models. We therefore point out a selective memory concerning functionality (primary level of memory (local)). However, ProteinMPNN, also recovers the main network of frustrated contacts of the functional domains even suggesting a tertiary level of memory (contacts). Thus, our approach promises to effectively unravel the intricacies of protein family boundaries and explore design options for understanding protein evolution.

4. Genetic Determinants of Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone Resistance in Children on Corticosteroid Treatment

Authors: Wisdom A Akurugu, Ekkehard Zöllner, Carel van Heerden and Nicola Mulder
Single nucleotide polymorphisms

Key words: ACTH resistance, Genetic marker, Genetic association, Inhaled corticosteroids
Asthma

Inhaled corticosteroids are crucial for managing asthma, but these may cause hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal suppression (HPAS). Cortisol production is suppressed as it is in Addison's Disease (AD), Clinical symptoms may be similar. Identifying genetic markers associated with ACTH resistance versus HPAS is crucial for precise patient stratification and personalized treatment. SNP data of ninety-six asthmatic children on inhaled corticosteroids and nasal steroids were studied. The participants underwent an overnight metyrapone test. Baseline adrenocorticotrophic hormone and cortisol were measured as well as post-metyrapone adrenocorticotrophic hormone (PMACTH). ACTH resistance was diagnosed if the PMACTH/C ratio is greater than 0.35. Eight-two and seventy-six samples out of the 96 participants had data for Basal and PM ACTH/C ratios respectively. SNP association was done using the PLINK analysis toolkit and statistical regression. Genetic models were assessed, and SNP functional annotation & prioritization were performed. Two significant SNPs emerged among others: rs6962 (G>A) on the SDHA gene and rs2303223 (G>A) on ZNF668 whereby rs6962 is likely resistant while rs2303223 is likely responsive to ACTH. Genotypic comparisons of rs6962 (AA vs GA & GG) and rs2303223 (GG vs GA & AA) showed statistical significance for $\sqrt{\text{BasalACTH/C}}$ and $\sqrt{\text{PMACTH/C}}$ ratios respectively. SDHA, integral to mitochondrial respiration, may affect metabolic pathways governing ACTH resistance. ZNF668, encodes a zinc finger protein and akin to other zinc proteins which are known to regular the glucocorticoid receptor (GR), may as well regulate the GR or other steroid receptors. Dysregulation of these genes could impact ACTH sensitivity. Further validatory and confirmatory investigations are recommended.

5. Interpretable deep generative ensemble learning of cell identity paired with automated annotation for single-cell multi-omics

Authors: Manoj M Wagle, Chunlei Liu, Ellis Patrick and Pengyi Yang

Key words: Single-cell omics, Single-cell multi-omics, Cell Identity, Feature Selection, Cell type annotation, Deep learning, Machine learning, Spatial omics

Single-cell omics technologies, with their recent advancement towards multi-modality, have achieved remarkable success in uncovering cellular heterogeneity at an unparalleled resolution. However, the high dimensionality, inherent noise, and sparsity render feature selection a crucial step in analyzing such data. Currently, the popular approach has been identifying highly variable genes, but this might not capture the complete spectrum of molecular variability and can miss out on certain informative genes. Moreover, the number of tools adept at capturing valuable information embedded in other single-cell modalities, such as chromatin accessibility and surface proteins, is currently limited. To bridge this gap, we have developed Hydra, an interpretable deep generative framework based on variational autoencoders and data augmentation. Unlike traditional methods, Hydra is capable of effectively utilizing diverse single-cell omics data to capture cell-type specific molecular signatures, enabling a holistic examination of cells within the dataset.

Additionally, as an integral component of this framework, we developed an ensemble classification module for the automated annotation of single-cell datasets. We extensively benchmarked Hydra across 23 datasets, including unimodal and multimodal single-cell and spatial transcriptomics datasets. Our results demonstrate that cell-type specific features selected by Hydra provide comparable to superior performance against several state-of-the-art methods in terms of stability, marker identification, cell-type annotation, and spatial deconvolution.

6. Unraveling patient heterogeneity through explainable AI and network-based strategies

Authors: Iria Pose-Lagoa, José Carbonell-Caballero, Beatriz Urda-García, Jon Sánchez and Alfonso Valencia

Key words: Machine Learning, feature selection, SHAP values, gene expression, COPD

Complex diseases often present a wide landscape of molecular profiles, posing challenges in identifying biomarkers associated with disease progression and, consequently, efficient personalized therapies. This is the case of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), a heterogeneous condition characterized by the development of severe airflow obstruction profiles. Here, we propose a comprehensive framework comprising three key components: feature selection, prediction performance, and SHAP values analysis. To achieve this, we used gene expression data from the Lung Tissue Research Consortium and employed various feature selection criteria to identify the most relevant discriminant genes. These filtering approaches include knowledge extracted from intrinsic data characteristics (data-driven), external information from DisGeNET of genes associated with COPD (curated COPD-related genes), and their respective biological expansions based on physical interaction partners (OmniPath) and network-based prioritization algorithms (GUILDify). Subsequently, we exhaustively evaluate the performance of several state-of-the-art classifiers: Random Forest, Support Vector Machines - polynomial and radial kernel, k-Nearest Neighbors, Generalized Linear Models, and XGBoost. SHAP values obtained from the most accurate settings were combined with clustering algorithms to explain the model's predictions and perform a cluster-based analysis for COPD profiling. Our integrative approach successfully distinguished COPD patients with data-driven selection strategy achieving the highest performance. These classifiers demonstrated accuracies of up to 84.8%, surpassing previous approaches. The genes identified in this study serve as promising biomarkers for COPD subtyping, offering avenues for more personalized treatment modalities. This study underscores the potential of integrated analytical approaches in advancing the diagnosis and treatment of complex diseases such as COPD.

Flash Talk (5 or 10 Minutes Slot)

TITLE: A - Z

1. Bridging Education and Research: Data Hunters Workshop Empowering Bioinformatics Education via Microbiome Studies

Authors: Sara Fumagalli, Giulia Ghisleni, Alice Armanni, Luca Corneo, Maurizio Casiraghi and Antonia Bruno

Key words: Student-Science activity, Bioinformatics education, Microbiome research, Metadata curation

Ensuring access to the bioinformatics field shall be on the agenda of life sciences degrees. This especially applies to biology-related degrees, where future biologists often ignore its existence due to the scarcity of dedicated courses. We present our contribution to bioinformatics education, using the Data Hunters Workshop as a case study. Kicked off on February 28th, Data Hunters constitutes an ongoing student-science activity for students of the University of Milano-Bicocca, particularly those in the Biotechnology and Biosciences Department. Combining educational engagement with scientific research, this initiative enables students to tackle the key issue of metadata standardization's lack in metagenomics, while supporting their learning. We provided a 6-hour lecture and an autonomous hands-on phase, structured as a learn-and-play activity with in-house built online educational and command-line resources. Thus, 29 students gained the fundamentals of metagenomics and Python language. Thanks to these tools, they have now stepped into the role of bioinformaticians, actively curating metadata from 379 amplicon-based and shotgun sequencing projects of the human skin microbiome to collaboratively create a curated metadata collection. Upon the workshop's conclusion, we will assess the efficacy of our activity via surveys and standardized evaluation scales.

Our workshop represents the effort to bridge educational and research aims, including students as bioinformaticians of the future. As a reflection of the synergy of our objectives, the workshop's outcomes will include significant educational impacts that will lead to the development of a collaborative curated collection of human skin microbiome metadata, alongside the advancement of bioinformatics dissemination.

2. Characterization of Non-Equilibrium Phase-Separated Biomolecular Condensates

Authors: Matthew Unger, Andrew Longhini and Kenneth S Kosik

Key words: Liquid-Liquid Phase-Separation, LLPS, Biomolecular condensates, Neurodegenerative Disease, Non-equilibrium, Biophysics

Biomolecular condensates, such as stress granules (SG), are understood to harbor protein aggregates implicated in neurodegenerative pathologies like Alzheimer's Disease (AD).

Understanding biomolecular condensate dynamics may therefore provide insight into potential therapeutic interventions for these diseases. Biomolecular condensates are formed by liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS). Under equilibrium conditions, multiple small droplets resulting from LLPS merge into a single large droplet. However, in living systems, phase-separated biomolecular condensates do not form large droplets and are instead maintained out-of-equilibrium as many small droplets. Molecular dynamics simulations run by our team suggested that this out-of-equilibrium behavior occurs due to an altered rate of switching between conformations of a biomolecule, with one state favoring phase separation and the other not. Based on this, we hypothesized that the faster a molecule switches between these two states, the further out-of-equilibrium and smaller the resulting biomolecular condensates will be. To investigate this, we used increasing cellular stress as a proxy for increasing swapping rate and explored the relationships between various stresses, ATP depletion, and SG sizes in a cell culture system. Additionally, we demonstrate that in vitro, phase-separated tau droplets remain smaller and more numerous when in the presence of the proline isomerase PPIA, compared to when PPIA is absent. By linking this PPIA to G3BP1, a core component of SGs, we showed that PPIA could control stress granule size. These findings together suggest that an out-of-equilibrium state can be maintained by an altered swapping rate of a biomolecule between two conformations.

3. Constructing representative sequence models for evolutionary analysis of protein superfamilies

Authors: Samuel Davis, Gabriel Foley, Marc Morris and Mikael Bodén

Key words: Protein evolution, Protein superfamilies, Phylogenetics, Sequence models

The ability to confidently infer evolutionary relationships at the scale of protein superfamilies would profoundly transform biology. While the advent of various machine learning-based models for sequence analysis have provided significant improvements in remote homology detection, it is unclear whether such methods can effectively reconstruct phylogenies at this scale. When analysing protein superfamilies, poor alignment accuracy presents a major hurdle to traditional phylogenetics. Additionally, the computational burden of performing these analyses on sufficiently large datasets may be prohibitive. These challenges are commonly exacerbated by input sequences which are poorly representative of the evolutionary space of interest. Curation approaches which rely on sequence similarity often produce unrepresentative sequences for alignment due to the diminishing correlation of sequence identity with evolutionary relatedness at high degrees of divergence. We developed an approach to minimise these issues which constructs representative profile Hidden Markov Models (pHMMs) for sequence curation from large evolutionary spaces. From pHMMs built with robust alignments of highly similar sequences, the tool iteratively expands the profiles' scopes. Their representativeness for the given space is optimised by systematic exclusion of sequence subsets and cross-validation over several iterations. Alignments and phylogenies constructed downstream of curation by this method demonstrate improvement across

various metrics. We applied this approach to investigate the evolutionary origins of B3 metallo-beta-lactamases, gaining novel insights into their emergence from a diverse superfamily. Enhancements in the alignment and phylogeny conferred by this tool allowed for characterisation of deep ancestral variants and new hypotheses regarding molecular determinants of this family's function.

4. Development and Application of the MultiSEp R Package to Identify Multiple Myeloma Achilles' Heels for Drug Discovery

Authors: Adeline McKie, Mark Wappett, Benayu Priyanto, Hans Vandierendonck and Ian Overton

Key words: Cancer, Multiomics, Gene Dependency Relationships, Synthetic lethality, R Package, Drug discovery, Data integration, Network biology, Clustering, Functional genomics, Multiple Myeloma, Precision oncology

Almost all Multiple Myeloma (MM) patients relapse and ultimately succumb to therapy-resistant disease; there is an urgent need for more effective treatment. Achilles' heel relationships arise when the status of one gene exposes a cell's vulnerability to perturbation of a second gene, such as chemical inhibition, providing opportunities for precision oncology. We developed MultiSEp for integrative discovery of candidate gene dependency relationships in multiomics data. We predicted MM GDRs at genome-scale (27,232 genes, 370,777,296 candidate interactions) using transcriptomic data from the Multiple Myeloma Research Foundation (MMRF) CoMMpass study (n=928 patients). Filtering steps to derive a high-confidence synthetic lethal network (SynLethNet) included predicting characteristic mutual exclusive loss patterns ($q < 0.05$). We predicted the population coverage achieved by drugging SynLethNet genes, and the impact of deleterious mutations. Our analysis only utilised deleterious mutations predicted by the variant effect prediction tools, SNPeff and SNPsift (annotated 'high-impact' mutations). We characterised GDRs in the CoMMpass cohort and derived a high confidence predicted synthetic lethal network (2,766 genes, 9,906 edges; SynLethNet). Functional annotation of SynLethNet revealed many genes involved in the ubiquitin-proteasome system, which is dysregulated in MM and a target of current front-line therapy. Predictions were validated with the Cancer Dependency Map and the Cancer Therapeutics Response database. We present the MultiSEp R package, demonstrated with a case study in Multiple Myeloma where we predict candidate drug targets and provide mechanistic insights to advance precision oncology.

5. FinaleToolkit: Accelerating Cell-Free DNA Fragmentation Analysis with a High-Speed Computational Toolkit

Authors: James W. Li, Ravi Bandaru and Yaping Liu

Key words: Cell-free DNA, Software toolkit, Computational biology, Bioinformatics, Cell-free DNA Fragmentomics, Epigenomics, Cancer Genomics, Genomics

The fragmentation pattern of cell-free DNA (cfDNA) represents a promising non-invasive biomarker for disease diagnosis and prognosis. Numerous fragmentation features, such as end motif and window protection score (WPS), have been characterized in cfDNA genomic sequencing. However, the analytical tools developed in these studies are often not released to the liquid biopsy community or are inefficient for processing large datasets. To address this gap, we have developed FinaleToolkit, a fast and memory-efficient Python package designed to generate comprehensive fragmentation features from large cfDNA genomic sequencing data. For instance, FinaleToolkit can generate genome-wide WPS features from a ~100X cfDNA whole-genome sequencing dataset in 74 minutes using 16 CPU cores and 49 GB of memory, offering up to a ~30-fold increase in processing speed compared to original implementations. We have benchmarked FinaleToolkit against existing studies or implementations where possible, confirming its efficacy. Furthermore, FinaleToolkit is open source and thoroughly documented with both command line interface and Python application programming interface (API) to facilitate its widespread adoption and use within the research community: <https://github.com/epifluidlab/FinaleToolkit>

6. First Draft Assembly and Annotation of the Genome of the Cadmium-Resistant Fungus *Talaromyces santanderensis* using Oxford Nanopore sequencing: First Molecular Insights into its Cadmium Resistance

Authors: Javier Correa Alvarez, Juan Picon Cossio, Andres Florian Cruz, Fabian Uhrlaub, Susana Sierra Pelaez and Carsten Harms

Key words: Genome de novo assembly, Genome de novo annotation, Oxford Nanopore, Cadmium resistance, Fungi, Methylome, Gene prediction

Contamination of crops soils by cadmium (Cd) is a worldwide threat to ecosystems and human health. High concentrations of Cd damage the cell membrane, organelles, and generate overproduction of reactive oxygen species. *Talaromyces santanderensis*, a recently fungal strain isolated from cocoa soil, is a new species of Cd resistant fungus with a high tolerance rating between 100–400 mg/kg. However, there is no molecular or genetic information about the mechanism used for tolerance. Thus, this study presents the first draft genome assembly and annotation of *T. santanderensis*. The genome of this strain was sequenced using Oxford Nanopore Technology with fungal DNA under stress conditions of Cd at 50 ppm, and under normal conditions of growth. The genome was assembled using Flye, Miniasm, NECAT, Wtdbg2 and Canu and produced assemblies exhibiting similarly high levels of BUSCO completeness (~96.5%) with a coverage of 20x on average. Flye presented the assembly with the highest contiguity featuring a N50 length of 8,443,216 bp and a maximum contig of 12,809,360 bp. The genome we present has a GC content of 45.16% and a size of 38,889,036 bp. Gene prediction yielded 13,791 genes, and through functional annotation we identified important homologous protein-coding genes reported to be associated with Cd resistance such as copper chaperone, arsenite and zinc transporter, arsenical resistance protein, and Cd²⁺-exporting ATPase. Additionally, we present *T. santanderensis* methylome for the modified bases 5mC and 5mhC during both

conditions, which will give us information about the role of the epigenomic in adaptation to heavy metal environment.

7. Multiomics analysis highlighted the role of senescence in regulating trophoblast differentiation: a promising target for early preeclampsia prediction

Authors: Jianlin Li, Qingqing Zhang, Cheuk-Lun Lee and Philip C.N. Chiu

Key words: Multiomics, Preeclampsia, Aging, CRISPR screening, CLEAR-CLIP

Background: Preeclampsia (PE) is a common gestational disease affecting 2-5% of all pregnancies, with its aetiology associated with defective trophoblasts differentiation. Currently, there is no reliable approach for either prediction or treatment of PE. Recent research highlights the significance of premature trophoblast senescence as a new characteristic of PE. Nonetheless, the molecular interactions between trophoblast senescence and differentiation are poorly understood.

Methods: We analyzed aging marker expression in trophoblast stem cells differentiating into extravillous trophoblasts (EVTs), identifying an aging-related gene set (ARGS). Using CRISPR knockout, we verified ARGS roles in trophoblast differentiation. Since miRNA is stable and allows easy PE diagnosis, we examined interactions between ARGS and miRNA using covalent ligation of endogenous argonaute-bound RNAs-crosslinking and immunoprecipitation (CLEAR-CLIP).

Results: Our findings demonstrated that the EVT differentiation process encompasses a senescence process, characterized by elevated levels of ARGS. By employing CRISPR-screening, we demonstrated that 41 genes (TD-ARGS) in ARGS are involved in regulating trophoblast differentiation. 91 miRNAs (TD-ARG miRNA) that interact with TD-ARGS in trophoblast were then identified using our CLEAR-CLIP data. To test the relevance of these TD-ARG miRNA to PE, we examined their expressions in the serum of first-trimester pregnant women. The levels of 4 TD-ARG miRNA was significantly different in women who later developed PE when compared to those with normotensive pregnancy.

Conclusion: The results of this study provide novel evidence that the senescence process is associated with trophoblast differentiation. Clinically, they also indicate the possible use of serum miRNA that targeting TD-ARG in the early prediction of PE."

8. Seven Domain Topics in Bioinformatics Education - Refining the ISCB Core Competencies to Access Diversity in Training

Authors: Nilson Da Rocha Coimbra, Bernardo Velozo, Clara Carvalho, Rayssa Feitosa, Lucas Aleixo Leal Pedroza, Emerson Danzer, Sandy Ingrid Aguiar Alves and Bibiana Fam

Key words: Topics Bioinformatics Education, ISCB Core-competencies, RSG-Brazil

The ISCB Regional Student Group of Brazil (RSG-Brazil) is at the forefront of promoting bioinformatics and computational biology education in Brazil. In 2019, RSG-Brazil launched its Educational Committee (EduComm) with a dual mission: to develop educational materials in Portuguese and to assess the efficacy of bioinformatics training in the country. Leveraging the ISCB core competency framework 3.0, the EduComm devised a novel training model to evaluate confidence in various technical aspects of bioinformatics. This model encompasses seven domain topics crucial for bioinformatics education: Biology, Statistics, Computer Science, Ethics, Bioinformatics Applications, Communication, and Professional Development. To gauge the educational needs of the Brazilian bioinformatics community, a survey was conducted in November 2023, collected 375 responses from across 21 states, predominantly from academia. Notably, the majority of respondents identified themselves as Bioinformatics Users, with a significant representation from Undergraduate and Graduate students. The survey revealed regional and profile-specific interests in Bioinformatics Topics, providing valuable insights for curriculum development. Through the efforts of EduComm, RSG-Brazil aims to tailor educational courses to meet the diverse needs of Brazil's computational biology student community. This work presents the findings from the survey conducted by RSG-Brazil's EduComm and highlights the importance of localized educational initiatives in advancing bioinformatics education on a global scale.

9. Utilizing a Novel VAE Pipeline for Tau Inhibitor Screening Validated in *Drosophila Melanogaster* Alzheimer's Models

Authors: Prisha Rai

Key words: Alzheimer's disease, Tau, Variational Autoencoder, Deep Learning, *Drosophila melanogaster*, RNA Extraction

Alzheimer's disease (AD), affecting over 50 million worldwide, is a progressive disorder characterized by Tau protein aggregation, leading to significant impairments. Current FDA-approved AD drugs target amyloid-beta aggregation, highlighting the need for alternative pathway approaches. This study introduces a novel approach integrating computational predictions with validations to identify therapeutic molecules against Tau aggregation. A variational autoencoder (VAE), using a Keras architecture, included a recurrent neural network (RNN) encoder and decoder and a property prediction model, with a gated recurrent unit (GRU) layer added to the decoder. The model was trained using the ZINC 250k Molecules Database and tested on a unique database of 72 known Tau inhibitors. The outputs synthesized Methylene Blue (MB), with validation loss sub-0.2 post 20 epochs. MB has been shown to inhibit Tau aggregation by accelerating LLPS. Administered to Alzheimer's mutant *D. melanogaster*, MB increased RNA concentration in Tau-mutated flies' brains. RNA quantification, a measure of transcriptional activity, validated MB's potential as a Tau inhibitor. This integrative approach highlights the efficacy of combining computational predictions with empirical testing in drug discovery.

Late Poster

TITLE: A - Z

1. Multiple spliced alignment

Authors: Châkirou Alabani and Aida Ouangraoua

Key words: Spliced alignment, Transcriptome, Consistency-based alignment

It is now well established that alternative splicing is a ubiquitous process in eukaryotic organisms that allows multiple distinct spliced transcripts to be produced from the same gene. Yet, the study of the evolution of sets of transcripts within a gene family is still in its infancy. One prerequisite for this study is the availability of methods to compare sets of transcripts while accounting for their splicing structure. In this context, a natural generalization of pairwise spliced alignment is multiple spliced alignment (MSPA) that is an alignment of a set of spliced RNA sequences with a set of unspliced genomic sequences. In addition to empowering the study of the evolution of sets of transcripts, MSPA has several other important purposes. For instance, it is a key to improving the prediction of gene models and structures, which is much needed to solve the current growing problem of genome annotation. We present the multiple spliced alignment problem, and a consistency-based alignment approach to compute the MSPA of a gene family. Like most multiple sequence alignment methods that are generally greedy heuristic methods that assemble pairwise sequence alignment information, SFAM is designed to combine all pairwise spliced alignments of CDS and gene sequences of a gene family into a MSPA. Using real vertebrates and simulated gene family data, we illustrate the utility of SFAM.

2. Sequence-based non-coding RNA classification

Authors: Ngone Thiam, Ibrahim Chegrane and Aida Ouangraoua

Key words: RNA classification, Machine learning, Feature selection

Non-coding RNAs classification is important for genome annotation and for functional analyses of these molecules. Efficient methods for large scale RNA classification remain challenging. Existing methods often rely on structure similarities, and they have huge time complexities due to the use of ncRNA secondary structure information, which prevent them from being used at large scale. We present a sequence-based method that relies on common sequence motifs computation to provide a set of features used for fast and accurate classification of ncRNAs families using a supervised learning approach. The experimental analysis shows that the method achieves comparable or more accurate classification than existing structure-based methods with drastically reduced processing times. For instance, compared to Infernal (Nawrocki-Eddy, Bioinformatics 2013), BlastN (Altschul et al., Journal of molecular biology 1990), ncRNA-deep (Noviello et al., PLoS computational biology 2020), our method allows to classify all RNAs of the Rfam database

(v14.1) families that contain at least 2 members (2636 families) with the highest accuracy (accuracy of 92.4% and F-beta score of 86.7) and the lowest processing time (one hour). These results demonstrate that, thanks to an appropriate selection of informative and discriminative conserved sequence motifs, it is possible to efficiently and accurately classify ncRNAs.

